

2025 MRS® SPRING MEETING & EXHIBIT

April 7-11, 2025 | Seattle, Washington

CALL FOR PAPERS

Abstract Submission Opens
Tuesday, September 17, 2024

Abstract Submission Closes
Thursday, October 17, 2024 (11:59 PM ET)

Symposium SU04: Protons in Solids, Fluids and Molecules -

Protons are essential lightweight building blocks in all organic materials, the dominating element in universe and basic constituent of water. Protons are intermediates in water splitting, carbon and nitrogen fixation reactions; they are small and can intercalate materials, form bonds with the host and become part of their structure. The proton is an important, yet elusive, ionic charge carrier in electrochemistry and virtually also a hydrogen carrier in proton pumps and hydrogen separation membranes. In nature, proton gradients across membranes serve the photo-induced production of chemical energy in cells, and involved into neuro transmission and cellular communication. Protons are the foundation of a hydrogen economy.

This symposium features the logistics of protons with respect to their importance to energy materials in technology and nature, in experiment and computational modeling: proton conductivity, hydrogen storage, fuel cells, and artificial photosynthesis and synapse networks. The symposium is the discussion platform where engineers and scientists from seemingly unrelated fields may find common ground for the transition from basic science to applied sciences and technology.

In addition to applications and devices, the symposium will include the important and frequently underestimated basic science of the proton hosted in solids; the transition from hydrogen bonding to proton-phonon coupling; and its benign or malign impact on functionality, stability, and integrity of materials. A further aspect is the proton transport in liquids and molecules, because it is important in biological systems including photosynthesis and the metabolism in living cells. Since hydrogen is taking center stage in a future clean and renewable energy technology and economy, we welcome also contributions from industries.

Topics will include:

- Protons in electrocatalysis and photocatalysis
- Ceramic proton conductors
- Polymer proton conductors
- Protons in biological energy conversion and catalysis
- Fuel cells and electrolyzers
- Protons as information carriers for signaling and neurotransmitters
- Molecular dynamics calculation for proton trajectories
- Measuring low and high hydrogen concentrations

Invited speakers include:

Kondo-Francois Aguey-Zinsou	University of Sydney, Australia	Igor Lubomirsky	Weizmann Institute of Science, Israel
Hyun S. Ahn	Yonsei University, Republic of Korea	Jörg Pieper	Tartu University, Estonia
Seukheun Choi	SUNY Binghamton, USA	Alexey Rulev	Empa - Swiss Federal Institutes of Technology, Switzerland
Huyen Dinh	National Renewable Energy Laboratory, USA	Noriko Sata	German Aerospace Center DLR, Germany
Chuancheng Duan	The University of Utah, USA	Sankaranarayanan Subramanian	University of Illinois, USA
Maria A. Gomez	Mount Holyoke College, USA	Massimo Trotta	IPCF Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Italy
Shu Hu	Yale University, USA	Paul Weiss	University of California Los Angeles, USA
Mantao Huang	Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA	Yoshihiro Yamazaki	Kyushu University, Japan
Min Hwan Lee	University of California, Merced, USA	Arthur Yelon	Polytechnique Montreal, Canada
Qiyang Lu	Westlake University, China	Bilge Yildiz	Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

Symposium Organizers

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